

TEACHING ENGLISH IN MIXED ABILITY CLASSROOMS

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ABSTRACT

The aim is to investigate teachers' perceptions on how they meet students' needs in a mixed-ability context. We listened to experienced teachers and analyzed their different ways of approaching mixed-ability classrooms. Our findings show that varied instruction is the best way to meet all pupils' needs and that it is necessary to have extra materials for both advanced and elementary students.

There is a variety of strategies that can be put into practice in order to meet all students' needs, but unfortunately, no "magic method" guarantees every student's development and success with regard to learning. In present time, English is the most preferred language. For the natives, learning English is a natural process. But for the students of other languages, we require big efforts to learn a foreign language. The students in Vietnam as well as in our school face such problems because English is not the mother tongue. Nowadays, most of the schools are with mixed ability students of different levels which are challenges to teachers.

Teacher's aim is to reach all the students by monitoring them in a variety of ways to achieve effective teaching. Almost of the students think English is a subject which they have to learn in school and do not realize English as a language of communication used globally.

To solve these problems, we need to have a systematic approach. We should aim teaching primarily not for knowledge but for skills. This paper deals with the problems of teaching English for students and defines different strategies in developing technique for dealing mixed ability classes to achieve better results in the teaching as well as in learning English.

Keywords: mixed-ability classes' problems and solutions, development of strategies and methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

English is a symbol of learners' aspirations for quality in education and it plays an important role in the field of communication over the world. Language learning is a natural process for the natives. In Vietnam, English is taught as a second language in educational institutes. Therefore, students find themselves unable to express what they want to say or to write in English. They have no idea of proper sentence structures, do not know how to pronounce correctly and spellings and grammatical rules. Moreover, most of the students interact in mother tongue inside the classroom. Grammar-Translation method is the redominant method of teaching English in most of the cases. Although webs of educational facilities are increasing rapidly, it has neither in raising the level of learners, nor made them learn English as a language. In mixed ability level teaching, the teacher finds out different strategies of teaching for different levels as Elementary, Pre-intermediate or Intermediate... to every learner, who has various potentialities, skills, interests and learning needs.

It is better that every student has a different way of learning, and progresses at different speeds. Most institutes in Vietnam, in general and English classes at HUF1, in particular, are usually multi-ability level. In order for teachers finding out teaching methods properly in such classes is really difficult and it is also a demanding task as it involves in planning lessons which consist of a diversity of tasks corresponding to a variety to learning styles and abilities. The classroom is the only environment for the learners where students could use this chance as much as possible. However, some of the students think it is difficult to speak a language with many reasons, ranging from interest to confidence. In contrast, other students express everything they think or feel by using the new language. As a result, some students are very active in class, while the others are very passive in class. Teachers try to identify the problems of mixed ability classes and give the solutions to eliminate them. There are several strategies that a teacher can use to deal this situation. This paper attempts to highlight the level of learning English, and the problems of teaching English for non-major students at HUF1 and some suggestions are given to improve the overall English language learning and teaching situation in mixed ability classrooms.

2 PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN MIXED ABILITY CLASSROOMS

In order to give all students, the chance to benefit from their lessons. It is necessary to design lesson plans or activities within the lesson properly. To be able to do that, English teachers need to know what are possible problems and solutions of working with multi-level classes. In addition, some of the possible problems which a teacher may encounter when working with students with different language ability can be summarized:

Most language text books are designed for an ideal homogenous class and students react in the different ways to them due to individual differences and preferred learning styles.

Possible problems:

A teacher might have difficulties in finding appropriate teaching materials and resources that fit the needs, individual language level and interest of all students.

The task included in the lesson should correspond to the language level, and abilities of learners.

Possible problems:

Slow learners cannot participate because the tasks are too difficult to them.

Every learner has individual interests and needs which form their attitude to the subject matter.

Possible problems:

The teacher doesn't know students 'level of interests and needs.

Some of the learners have difficulties in speaking the target language for various reasons, while the other learners are willing to express their thoughts and ideas in the target language. As a result, some students participate actively in the lesson and the others do not.

Possible problems:

Active students tend to attract the teacher's attention while shy learners are limited.

Students work with different pace. Those who have an advanced level master the tasks in the lesson quickly or get impatient when the teacher has to repeat an explanation, while students who have a lower level of knowledge and skills complete the tasks more slowly.

Possible problems:

Active learners finish the tasks given quickly whereas the weaker ones can not complete in time and may lose their confidence. Consequently, mixed abilities may result in classroom management problems.

3 POSSIBLE WAYS TO OVERCOME THE EFFECT IN MIXED ABILITY CLASSROOMS

The teacher should

- adapt some of the materials to make the language simple.
- design own teaching materials.
- use visual teaching materials to attract the students' attention and to motivate them to get interest in the subject.
- vary the level of tasks to the slow learners, for example, should not give the more difficult choices in multiple level exercises.
- set up groups of weaker and stronger students separately and give different tasks to these groups, for example, stronger and quicker students are assigned to do more complicated tasks, whereas the weaker students deal with simpler tasks or work with the teacher as a group member.
- try to know the learners, their language level and interests.
- try to find every single students' strength by offering a variety of activities.
- try to find the strengths and preferred learning style of every one.
- encourage the shy learners.
- the teacher should give extra work that students would enjoy doing on their favorite topic.
- help students to improve their skills and abilities.
- prepare additional activities for the active learners.

4 STRATEGIES AND METHODS

In the English courses at HUF1, the teaching of English as a communication language is an integral part of the curriculum or the course obligations. The learners do not realize the importance of English as a language of communication and they lack the confidence when they communicate in English. The main reason is that they have been taught the language through grammar-translation method. This method made them depend on their mother tongue. So, the students need more practice for testing proficiency.

5 SAMPLE TESTING

A set of ten students of the first year studying HCM city University of Food Industry (HUF1), was randomly selected for testing. A questionair which contains ten questions of English grammar with a translation passage was given to them in order to answer. The following result is

Course : General English

Sample group size : 10

Number of fast learners : 4

Number of slow learners : 6

Total number of questions	Very good	Good	Poor
10	1	3	6
100%	10%	30%	60%

During the analysis, there were many kinds of errors in most of the sentences which are made by the fresh students at HUF1 indicated the poor learning condition of the learners. To solve all the problems, a systematic approach should be followed. The teacher should find some ways of helping learners to enjoy their language activities and of building their confidence. To handle the problems of lacking in learning language. The students should be made to train with some simple practices.

Some sample questions for testing the various aspects of skills:

A. Testing pronunciation

Choose the odd one out

- | | | | |
|-----------------------|--------------------|-------------------|--------------------|
| 1. A. <u>decided</u> | B. <u>tested</u> | C. <u>invited</u> | D. <u>loved</u> |
| 2. A. <u>students</u> | B. <u>teachers</u> | C. <u>Leaves</u> | D. <u>machines</u> |
| 3. A. <u>hour</u> | B. <u>house</u> | C. <u>home</u> | D. <u>high</u> |
| 4. A. <u>walk</u> | B. <u>work</u> | C. <u>warm</u> | D. <u>war</u> |
| 5. A. bedroom | B. bathroom | C. kitchen | D. vegetable |
| 6. A. architect | B. apple | C. meat | D. fish |

B. Testing vocabulary

1. Match the words with the definitions.

- | A | B |
|------------------|---|
| 1. to sponsor | a. a person who competes in a sport |
| 2. a range | b. a journey, often to a place that is not well known |
| 3. to expand | c. to support a project by giving money |
| 4. an expedition | d. a variety of products that people can buy |
| 5. an athlete | e. to become bigger |

2. Find other words that go together with make and get

C. Testing structures

1. Use the correct form of the verb in brackets, Past Simple or Present Perfect.

In recent years *The North Face* **has had** problems with people making illegal copies of its products.

The North Face **has opened** eleven stores in Europe since 2003.

In 2005 *The North Face* **expanded** its store in Livorno, Italy.

The North Face **has advertised** its products in serious sports magazines for many years.

Ten years ago *The North Face* **launched** TekWare, a new range of sportswear.

2. Complete the questions with the words given in the present perfect tense.

1. lose / something important?
2. win / a competition?
3. be / on television?

3. Rewrite these words into a complete sentence.

1. How / are / in / students / there / class / many ?
2. morning / usually / get / in / My / at / six / mother / up / o'clock / the.

Such practices will help the students attract in their lesson. They can understand the importance of grammar and strengthen their skills. Apart from such practices, the following strategies can also be adopted in learning language in class.

Encouragement: A teacher is more effective when he/she is able to highlight the positive qualities of a student. It is important to point out the small success of the student, which may lead to big successes tomorrow.

Non-correction methods: In developing the skill of communication in English, correction must be avoided. If the teacher corrects a student as soon as he/she starts speaking, he dare not speak in front of other people because he is afraid of make mistakes again. The best thing is to help students to speak at least the wrong English.

Word-Building: There are three levels of word power built in generally and steadily through experiencing the language. The first set of word is that a student will be able to identify but he may not know the correct meaning , and hence hesitate to use while speaking or writing. The second set of words is that a student will be able to identify and understand the meaning but he is unable to use as the situation demands. The third set of words may be the half of the number of the second set, a student becomes capable of speaking when he he has a collection of words. The teacher has to work continuously to increase the word store for students.

Reading and Comprehension: In class, the teacher should give students an opportunity to read aloud, so that students can hear that words spoken by him. In addition, Students can comprehend what he reads. And this will help them to identify easily for the leading questions.

Models of Listening: Including several types of conversations and speeches. The best available methods are to provide recorded conversations for the students in the lesson. Initially, the conversations will be a imitative, but gradually, through repetitions, the students will outgrow the imitative method and attempt to speak by using their own words, structures and patterns.

Along with all such practices in the classroom, it is also neccessary to arrange group discussion in class. Their enthusiasm for learning will help them in their own advancement. The problems of the students and the teachers are inter-related. The problems can be solved effectively if we take into consideration the role the teachers and students in gaining the knowledge of a language. Only when the students realize the practical use of English language. English will be use as an medium of expression and as a language of communication. The teacher's role and job rests not only in teaching the subjects but in recreating young minds as well. It is well known that every student learns and progresses at different speeds. Thus, effective strategies help students face the competition and challenges.

6 CONCLUSION

The role of teacher is to identify and find out the effective strategies and to implement an active, interesting and interact process of learning for the students with different levels of ability. Teachers must have healthy and congenial relationship with them. The teacher must teach, motivate and recreate minds in order that students are capable to facing challenges and overcome the difficult problems.

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